

Research

Use Of Neuro-linguistic Programming (NLP) techniques in the perspectives of college teachers to help learners deal with anxiety issues

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Abstract: The study aims to answer how far is Neurolinguistic Programming (NLP) known to college teachers and based on teachers' perspectives; if its techniques are effective in dealing with anxiety issues of college learners at APSACS, Petaro, Sindh, Pakistan. NLP is an interdisciplinary approach that is studied to analyse its strategies to reach a personal objective, it involves thoughts, language and patterns of behaviour learned by experiencing a particular outcome. Firstly, the researcher has identified the NLP techniques that are used to deal with the anxiety of learners that becomes a hindrance in the classroom learning and reaching learning outcomes, for which, Zeb and Hameed (2020)'s study is adopted. Secondly, qualitative method of research is followed with an interview protocol which posed questions to college teachers about the awareness of the NLP, the NLP strategies used by them and the effectiveness of these strategies. The researcher has applied following steps to reach at the conclusion; identifying NLP strategies; conducting workshop for college teachers for their awareness of the field, interviewing the college teachers and lastly, analysing the data. Findings show that teachers were not aware of the field or strategies by their actual terms before the workshop provided by the researcher but agreed to be using them effectively for years in the classes subconsciously when dealing with learners who suffer with anxiety.

Keywords: Neurolinguistic Programming, interdisciplinary approach, anxiety, qualitative method

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Introduction

Neurolinguistic Programming (NLP) is an approach that can enable the teachers to at least comprehend an essential part of the world using learners' senses through sensory systems, belief, knowledge, and perceptions. NLP helps in

achieving learners' excellence in their performance and its techniques and tools can be used in developing rapport, action, learners' achievement, and teaching efficiency (Keezhatta, 2019). It helps in achieving teachers' goals in making the learning cost-effective and productive to motivate several learners into joining and learning attentively in the class. NLP is an experience that is based on subjective grounds that improves our interpersonal communication skills. The different strategies adopted in dealing with anxiety of learners on an auditory, kinaesthetic, or visual level; can be achieved by developing materials for it or present surrounding such as pictures, sounds or even our emotions. These strategies can be adapted depending on individual learners' difference to help learners deal with their issues and reach to an effective result. This is achieved by its techniques, for instance, swishing which is about eliminating the stimulus that causes harm. NLP techniques and strategies have been used in the advance-teaching program because of its importance in developing the communication skills and improving knowledge which play significant role in teaching-learning process. Also, NLP helps teachers to analyse and understand their students' preferred learning styles. The communication between learners and teachers can be adjusted because of NLP offering flexibility. Aspects of NLP, for example, its meta-model which is a set of linguistic patterns for authentic information collection is also used for promoting student's learning (Kudliskis, 2014).

This paper aims at investigating how far the NLP techniques prove successful by the teachers for the learners at college level having anxiety issues to promote classroom learning. To fulfil the aim of this paper following objective is devised: To identify the success rate of NLP techniques used by college teachers on students having anxiety issues at APSACS, Petaro, Sindh, Pakistan.

Literature Review

According to Tosey and Mathison (2009), NLP training has been taken by more than 200,000 people in the United States and the United Kingdom. According to Sturt (2012), the organization called National Health Services (NHS) in the United Kingdom, has worked on the development of NLP and its hundreds of facilities, and had invested around £800,000 between the years 2006 and 2009. The UK Council of Psychotherapy (UKCP) also identified Neuro-Linguistic Therapy in the 1990s, as because of its proper usage NLP can help assess the clinicians to understand the internal world of the patients that they go through, based on the application of sub-modalities and strategies (Kotera, 2019). Confirming to the positive effect of NLP, according to Nomp (2021), NLP is a communicative field that employs a motivative view and helps changing and positively shaping the life. Nomp (2021)'s studies show how NLP can establish effective communication and can help deal with anxiety and can encourage changes in a person's behaviour patterns. There are number of NLP techniques including sensory acuity, reframing, anchoring, rapport, and pacing, and leading. NLP can improve knowledge, capabilities and attitudes, communication skills, self-management, mental health, it can reduce work stress, and self-efficacy.

Research Methodology

This study aims to investigate the awareness and effectiveness of NLP techniques when used by college teacher to deal with learners' anxiety that can hinder their learning process. This research is designed in qualitative nature. To have an insight view of this study, semi-structured interviews were conducted based on thematic analysis. The methodology of the paper was designed to help teachers get aware of the NLP practices that can predict and minimize the anxiety issues with learners and figure out its success rate. There are two goals for the study. First is to interview the teachers and find out about the NLP practices implemented in the classroom on the learners. The second is to know what regarding to them the success rate of NLP practice is. With semi-structured interviews, the open-ended nature of the question explains the topic under investigation, but also grants opportunities for the interviewer and interviewee to discuss the topic in more detail. If the interviewee has issue answering a question or provides only a brief response, the interviewer can use cues or

prompts to encourage the interviewee to consider the question further (Fox, 2000). This is what was done by the research, who kept a handout of the NLP techniques to explain it to the participants, a semi-structured questionnaire that led to more discussions on the topic and journal and phone to keep record of participants' answers.

Data Sampling

For the sampling, nine teachers in total were selected for the interview in which five teachers taught XI class and four teachers taught XII class students at APSACS, Petaro, Sindh, Pakistan. The sample from the population was selected from the stratified sample method.

Data Collection and Procedure

This research is based on discussing the awareness of NLP practices for minimizing anxiety issues with learners and to find out the degree to which it proves successful by taking their interviews individually based on thematic analysis. A semi-structured questionnaire was made by the researcher which included introductory questions about NLP and its practices in the classrooms. Participants were also asked if they found these practices effective for learners. The participants were nine senior teachers who taught college students and were selected for in-depth interviews. The focus was to find out about the awareness of the research topic and to reach a conclusion if NLP proved successful. The researcher kept a research journal and a phone to record the conversation throughout the data collection process. She also kept a handout of the explanation of NLP techniques if a participant needed a revision of what the technique meant.

The journal entries made by the researcher included notes on the researcher's perceptions of the participants and collections of what and how the participants reacted and spoke during the interviews. These notes helped the researcher to note down the important points of what participants said in the interviews during the analysis process and identified if any elaborations or remarks by the participants were important to be added to the findings, while the recordings were used for analysing participants' interpretation and responses to the questions.

This is not an "objective" data source; rather, it is subjective. In the journal and phone, the researcher recorded all personal impressions that could have an impact on the analysis procedures. By recording subjective information of this kind by the researcher, it was possible to make notes on what should be guarded against or in favour regarding the subjectivity during the process of analyses.

Coding of the Data

Considering the research ethics, the researcher has given codes to participants' names to secure their identities. The information about the nine interviewees (as participants) is tabulated below:

Table 1.1

Serial No.	Information	Code for Participants
1.	College Teacher	Prt. 1
2.	College Teacher	Prt. 2
3.	College Teacher	Prt. 3
4.	College Teacher	Prt. 4
5.	College Teacher	Prt. 5
6.	College Teacher	Prt. 6
7.	College Teacher	Prt. 7
8.	College Teacher	Prt. 8
9.	College Teacher	Prt. 9

Findings and Discussion

Thematic analysis is a practical data analysis approach for qualitative researchers; clarifying how to use it appropriately and effectively can help researchers recognize its utility and versatility (Kiger & Varpio, 2022). In thematic analysis, the research is organized and structured based on observations in accordance with the recurrent themes in the responses of the participants. They maintain that a theme should also represent some level of a structured meaning or response within a dataset. Considering these understandings, the researcher has derived the recurrent themes for a thematic analysis through the process of coding as illustrated above in Table 1.2. The derived themes with their respective analyses are described below:

Table 1.2

S. No.	Research Question	Participants' statements/responses	Codes	Themes
1.	How aware are the teachers at the college level regarding NLP practices in classroom learning?	"Neurolinguistic Programming as a term is completely unfamiliar to me, though when you explained what they were about, I realized I already knew them"	Lack of Awareness Unfamiliarity with NLP terms	Teachers' Awareness and understanding about the usage of NLP
2.	What are the NLP techniques used in classroom learning by the teachers at college level to minimize learners' anxiety?	"I utilize all the techniques, just today I was engaged in a task in the classroom utilizing all the resources around me to make the student understand my point" "yes I try to not taking student's name, and prefer saying words like all or everyone, as you know I wouldn't want to personally attack on the learner knowing they are having anxiety issues"	NLP techniques Using present resources Universal Quantifier	Application of NLP techniques by the Teachers
3.	How far do NLP techniques prove successful according to college teachers when applied in the classroom learning to	"These techniques are very much effective.." "I do not use them every time on regular basis, just once in a while, but whenever I get to face such challenges, I do use	Effectiveness of NLP techniques Success rate of NLP techniques	Teachers' Perspectives Regarding the effectiveness of NLP

	minimize learners' anxiety?	these techniques and they work"		
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Teachers' Awareness and understanding about the usage of NLP

The question from the developed interview protocol for this study was "What was your knowledge about NLP before the workshop you attended?" led researcher to conclude upon participants' own opinions as what was their awareness regarding Neurolinguistic Programming before attending the workshop that we worked upon. When interviewed, none of the teachers who were part of the research had awareness of NLP terms. Prt. 1 "I did not know about NLP, neither had I heard the term before". Though, when the terms were explained to them, they expectedly said that they already were familiar with the usage and subconsciously had the knowledge of all of them as they were implementing them in class unknowingly. Prt. 2 said "Neurolinguistic Programming as a term is completely unfamiliar to me, though when you explained what they were about, I realized I already knew them". Many of the teachers said there was no such training or course that has been offered to them before, which could be the reason leading to unfamiliarity of the term but they are indeed comprehensible. As Prt. 9 said "I was not aware of the terms before I attended the workshop, neither got such training before, but I've been passively knowing them". Prt. 8 said "Now that you have explained the terms to me, I do understand what they are about'. Prt.3 said "Oh I have been using them all these years in my teaching experience, did not know them by their terms though".

The researcher had already expected those answers, as when opting for this research topic, as a teacher, I was completely unfamiliar with the terms, but exploring through the number of studies, I understood how we teachers tend to use so many strategies and techniques without acknowledging the fact that this could be related to a field already struggling to be known by its actual term. Most of the teachers agreed to be using the NLP strategies throughout their teaching experience, but none was familiar with what Neurolinguistic Programming or its strategies were.

Application of NLP techniques by the Teachers

Adapted from Zeb & Hameed (2020)'s Study; participants were provided with the handout of NLP techniques' explanation for better understanding and communication. When I asked them about implementing any of the NLP techniques mentioned in the given handout after explaining what the strategy meant, they said they were already incorporating NLP techniques for years as teachers on dealing with students' anxiety. Prt. 1 said "I utilize all the techniques, just today I was engaged in a task in the classroom utilizing all the resources around me to make the student understand my point'. Answering to one of the strategies, that said if the teachers focus on student's past to make them feel guilty of their mistakes, to which Prt. 7 said; "I never stress on past". Prt. 6 said "I think that would make the student feel upset or worse, I tell them to focus on the present for the better tomorrow". Similarly, Prt. 5 said; "I use the techniques on regular basis, to motivate them". Prt. 3 said "for the commands and tasks, I assigned a student to be prefect of the college, to change his behaviour, for motivation and for him to be responsible and engaged, this really worked out for me, previously he would only spend time with his classmates and won't focus on the studies despite of having great abilities, now he has become responsible and aware of his capabilities".

Moreover, the researcher specifically asked about the NLP techniques after discussing what these were and they quoted their real-life classroom examples how they have been using on dealing anxiety that become a hindrance in the learning process of the students. Prt 6. said; "oh I never stress on past but try to make the learner focus on their current performance". Prt. 7 said; "I take usage of surrounding, like marker, book or board where I feel I can make them understand with...". Prt. 8 said; "I tell the learner to stay positive, please think about yourself achieving something.". On asking about Universal Quantifier strategy of NLP; Prt. 9 said "yes I try to not taking student's name, and prefer saying words like all or everyone, as you know I wouldn't want to personally attack on the learner knowing they are having issues". Prt. 8 said; "oh yes I do that a lot, this works and the student gets the message and gets attentive in the

class." I also asked if they are applying the strategy of Presupposition on dealing with students' anxiety, to which they were affirmative that this helps learners to get motivated. Prt. 5 said; "yes, I make them imagine of them achieving big in life and having all the potential that is needed to be successful and happy". When all the participants agreed to using commands as techniques, but Prt. 4 disagreed saying; "I do not go for commands, rather this term is quite discouraging for me".

The researcher also asked them if they would continue using the NLP techniques when dealing with learners with anxiety to which all the teachers agreed. Prt. 1 said; "oh yes yes very much! this is how I've been dealing and continue". Prt. 3 said; "yes, in case if I learn other strategies that would help me overcome anxiety of the students, I follow these and I would keep on applying".

Teachers' Perspectives Regarding the effectiveness of NLP

Proceeding with the interviews' data, teachers were asked if the NLP techniques, after using them for years, prove effective, the common answer was a 'yes.' I believe NLP techniques' motive of achieving positive result is useful, especially when the learners who have already got the potential that needed to be realized by them. As Prt. 1 said "yes these techniques are very much effective, in fact I used it with a student suffering from anxiety and discouragement, I assigned the tasks and communicated to get a positive response and to my achievement she is now outperforming in the class". Whereas, two teachers said they seldom use NLP techniques when it comes to students suffering with anxiety. Prt. 6 said; "I use the techniques but generally do not think about these when dealing with their anxiety, I talk to them in person, though the techniques should be promoted so teachers could know more about it.". Prt. 7 said "I do not use them every time on regular basis, just once in a while, but whenever I get to face such challenges, I do use these techniques and they work". Prt 3 said; "oh I have been using these techniques for years now, just did not realize what they were termed, there was a student who used to stay quiet, she would struggle to communicate the issues and would not improve, I motivated her continuously and it was just this that she needed, she topped in the exam, I knew she had this potential". NLP techniques have proved to be successful as they have been used for years without the teacher knowing.

According to all the teachers I interviewed, they said that NLP techniques were effective whenever they faced students struggling with anxiety issues, these techniques should be promoted. On asking about its affectivity, Prt 9 said; "absolutely! They play a key role in maximizing the learning goals and minimizing students' issues that hinder their success." Prt 5 said, "yes they should be promoted and workshops should be given to teachers so they can know more about the NLP techniques". Overall, out of all the teachers, they agreed that the techniques are indeed effective when dealing with students' anxiety, it develops a bridge that promotes communication between a student and teacher.

Conclusion

Neurolinguistics, being the interdisciplinary field, has been achieving notable progress for those who implement it. This study, which is carried out qualitatively by taking in-depth interviews with the college teachers, does reveal the positive affectivity and changes of it as what the field claims. The teachers agreed to be using the NLP strategies for years and witnessing the positive changes in learners when it comes to them dealing with anxiety issues, and talked about it should be promoted to raise awareness of it. However, this study does need to be promoted through trainings and workshops and explored on so many academic levels and aspects of mental challenges so that the stakeholders acknowledge the importance of it and implement them to achieve the learning outcomes and fight against mental and psychological challenges.

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